

Resin-catalyzed hydrolysis of some esters in aqueous and non-aqueous mixtures

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Manuscript received 17 August 2001, revised 20 November 2002, accepted 25 February 2003

The catalytic hydrolysis of ethyl, butyl and isobutyl acetates in aqueous solution and aqueous organic mixtures in presence of cation exchange resin in the hydrogen form was studied. The acid resin, however, behaved in aqueous organic mixtures in the same way as such resins do in pure water. The order of the chemical reaction in the heterogeneous catalysis by the resin was found to be the same as in the homogenous catalysis by a dissolved electrolyte. This was considered to indicate that the reaction mechanism is essentially the same in both cases. The overall rate was controlled by the chemical reaction of the ester at the catalytically active sites within the resin. The activation parameters were calculated for all the investigated reactions.

The overall rate of the resin-catalyzed hydrolysis of esters is controlled¹ by (i) film diffusion, (ii) chemical reaction within the catalyst particles and (iii) chemical reaction at the particle surfaces. For a given amount of catalyst (resin) with both (i) and (iii), the rate is inversely proportional to the particle size of the former. Internal reaction control (ii) is established when the overall rate with a given amount of the catalyst is independent of the particle size. The acid resin catalyzed hydrolysis of esters has been studied²⁻⁶. Several workers⁷⁻⁹ have studied the mechanism of the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate catalyzed by ion exchange resins of the type Dowex 50W. They investigated the effect of resin cross-linking and the initial reactant ratio on the conversion.

In the present work, we are concerned with the acid hydrolysis of esters and for this reason the strongly acidic cation exchange resin KU2-20 was used in the hydrogen form as the catalyst. One of our objectives was to treat quantitatively the kinetics of the catalysis of ester hydrolysis by ion exchanger and to compare it with that of the homogeneous system.

Results and discussion

The esters chosen for study were all acetates; so the effect of varying one structural parameter at a time could be investigated (Fig. 1). The esters used were the ethyl, butyl and isobutyl acetates. Simple first order kinetics were found to be followed in each case. The acid concentration was kept effectively constant during each run and the pseudo-first order rate constants obtained for all three acetates are listed in Table 1. In all cases the order of the chemical reaction was found to be the same as in homogeneous catalysis by a dissolved electrolyte. This emphasized that the reaction mechanism was the same in both cases. In the first order rate equation,

$$K_r = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{T_\infty}{T_\infty - T_t} \quad (1)$$

K_r is the rate constant (per g of resin) of the heterogeneous reaction and T_t and T_∞ are the volumes of titre at time t and at infinity, respectively. However, there were differences in the values of reaction rate constants (Table 1) for heterogeneous and homogeneous systems, even when the amount of catalyst (in counter - ion equivalents) was the same. The difference is claimed to be due to interaction of ester with the resin matrix, diffusion effects, and salting in of reactants. Many such phenomena can be described as related to the difference in solvent composition in the proximity of the resin matrix, compared to the composition in the

Fig. 1. Effect of varying structural parameters on the percent conversion at 69°.

Table 1. Rate constants and activation parameters for the catalyzed hydrolysis of esters

Ester	Temp. °C	K_r $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$	E_a kJ mol^{-1}	ΔG^* kJ mol^{-1}	ΔH^* kJ mol^{-1}	$-\Delta S^*$ e.u.	q	$-\Delta\Delta S^*$ e.u.
Ethyl acetate	78	13.4	77.55	80.75	74.63	17.44	1.01	3.48
	69	7.02		80.44	74.71	16.75	1.00	3.61
Butyl acetate	58	2.69		80.41	74.80	16.94	1.03	3.47
	78	8.32	62.10	82.13	59.18	65.40	1.00	5.38
	69	5.12		81.34	59.25	64.56	1.01	5.51
Isobutyl acetate	58	2.30		80.84	59.35	64.93	1.05	5.41
	78	7.80	65.73	82.33	62.81	55.62	1.10	0.78
acetate	69	4.60		81.64	62.89	54.83	1.02	1.42
	58	2.00		81.22	62.98	55.12	1.11	0.78

bulk of the solution. The rate constant increased in the order : isobutyl < *n*-butyl < ethyl acetate.

The efficiency of the resin (q) which is the ratio of the rate constants in the heterogeneous and homogeneous system with equivalent amounts of catalyst was larger than unity and increased with increasing molecular weight of the ester (Table 1). This means that the ion exchanger as a catalyst was more effective than an equivalent amount of hydrochloric acid in the process of the ester hydrolysis¹⁰.

The results of studying the effect of varying the ratio of dioxane and ethanol on the kinetics of hydrolysis of ethyl acetate are given in Table 2. It was found that with increasing percentage of organic solvent in solution, the values of percent conversion decrease whereas the time of attaining equilibrium increases (Fig 2).

A linear relationship is found between the percent of dioxane and ethanol added by volume to reaction medium

Table 2. Rate constants of heterogeneous catalyzed hydrolysis of ethyl acetate at 69°

Solvent %(v/v)	Amount of catalyst	Percent conversion	K_r $\times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Ethanol	0.0	1	80
	3.0	1	72
	6.0	1	67
	9.0	1	50
Dioxane	0.0	1	80
	3.0	1	55
	6.0	1	35
	9.0	1	22
Aqueous medium	3		82
	6		83
	8		86
	10		87

Fig. 2. Effect of ethanol percentage on the percent conversion of the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate.

and the value of specific rate constant which is found to decrease regularly. The highest value of K_r is obtained for the aqueous medium as compared with the values in presence of different ratios of organic solvent used. Ethanol and dioxane lowered the dielectric constant¹¹ and they decreased the rates as expected^{12,13}. These additives retarded the rates for all compositions employed, and at equimolar concentration, the magnitude of decrease of rate constant was greater in case of dioxane. The rate of reaction and percent conversion decrease with increasing quantity of dioxane content due to non-bonded¹⁴ interactions between the carbonyl carbon and water molecule. The rates of the acid hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in ethanol-water mixtures decrease with increasing organic component in solvent mixtures because (i) water concentration decreases on successive addition of ethanol, (ii) a water molecule involved in hydrogen bond formation with alcohol molecule is less nucleophilic than that in-

volved in hydrogen bond formation with another water molecule, (iii) addition of ethanol to water lowers the dielectric constant of the medium. Thus from an electrostatic viewpoint, a rate decrease might be expected because of destabilization of the polar transition state when the bulk dielectric constant is lowered by successive addition of the alcohol¹⁵. Since the highly polar transition state is more strongly solvated relative to the less polar ground state, it is expected that as the solvent polarity decreases, the reaction rate decreases.

A set of experiments was done especially to study the effect of particle size of the resin on the rate of the reaction. The cation exchange resin of particle diameters equal to 0.05, 0.03 mm was used in the hydrolysis of ethyl acetate in the temperature range 58–78°. The overall rate was independent of the particle size of the resin and accordingly the rate-determining step was the reaction of the ester at the catalytically active sites within the exchanger (internal reaction control)¹.

The results given in Table 2 and Fig. 3 show that at relatively small H⁺ ion concentrations the value of specific rate constant is low, the time necessary for attaining equilibrium is long, and the percent conversion is relatively low. Further increase of H⁺ ion concentration of the resin is accompanied by an increase in the value of specific rate constant and percent conversion and a decrease in the time necessary for reaching equilibrium.

The thermodynamic properties of the activated complex usually are of interest to interpret the data obtained in the present investigation in terms of the values of the activation parameters (Table 1). The activation energy E_a was determined from Arrhenius relation⁹. The change of enthalpy

Fig. 3. Representation of the first order equation for ethyl acetate at various amounts of catalyst.

of activation (ΔH^*) was evaluated from the relation¹⁶,

$$\Delta H^* = E_a - RT \quad (2)$$

The change of free energy of activation (ΔG^*) was deduced from Eyring's eqn.,

$$K_r = \frac{kT}{h} e^{-\Delta G^*/RT} \quad (3)$$

The change in entropy of activation (ΔS^*) was calculated from the relationship,

$$\Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^* \quad (4)$$

The quantity $\Delta\Delta S^*$ is the difference between the change in entropy of activation of the heterogeneous system and that of the homogeneous system, and it is an important factor in determining the efficiency. The reactant molecule suffers a loss of some internal degrees of freedom during the process of the formation of the activated complex within the resin. Reactant molecules with many internal degrees of freedom have more entropy to lose. For these reasons ΔS^* and $\Delta\Delta S^*$ become negative (Table 1). Consequently, the efficiency is small and its temperature coefficient is negative, i.e. the activation energy of heterogeneous catalysis is less than that of homogeneous catalysis. The value of $\Delta\Delta S^*$ increased in the following order: *n*-butyl < ethyl < isobutyl acetate. This order represents the sequence of probability for the formation of the activated complex. The smaller the ester molecule, the more easier would be its mobility to the active sites within the resin. During the formation of the activated complex, the loss of the internal degree of freedom for the straight-chain ester molecules was greater than that for the branched chain ones. The ΔH^* values increase gradually with increasing temperature, which may be a direct consequence of the increase of the activation energy with increase of molecular weight^{8,10}. The positive values of the heat of activation also increase with increasing branching of the ester isobutyl acetate > *n*-butyl acetate. The ΔG^* values are independent of the resin structure and are not greatly dependent on the temperature of the reaction. This shows that the stability of the transition state is very little affected by the temperature and so ΔH^* changes in accordance with the variation of ΔS^* values.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The cation exchange catalyst used in the present work was KU2-20 resin in the hydrogen form (0.05 mm). The reaction rates were determined with the batch operation at 58, 69, and 78° with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^\circ$. To double-distilled water (100 ml), air-dried ion exchange resin in the hydrogen form (1g)

and the desired volume of ester were added. The experimental technique was that described previously⁶. The specific rate constants were determined in different dioxane and ethanol mixtures containing 0.0 to 9.0% (v/v).

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